

Sensing the Crowd: Neural Mechanisms of Social Group Detection in Zebrafish

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ABSTRACT

Animals constantly adapt their behavior to changes in their environment. As social animals process external inputs, their neuronal response leaves a quantifiable trace that allows to study how individuals perceive and interact with others and offers an insight into the neural basis of social behavior. In this study, we analyzed how social density is translated in the brain of *Danio rerio* larvae using two genetic markers, *pth2* and *c-fos*. The neuropeptide *pth2* is expressed in dorsal thalamus cells and reflects social environment, whereas *c-fos* is an immediate early gene indicating general and recent neuronal activity. Larvae were distributed in five different density groups (1,2,5,20 or 50 individuals), fixed, and processed using Hybridization Chain Reaction (HCR). After that, brains were imaged under a confocal microscope and fluorescence-based measurement showed that *pth2* expression increased with group size, whereas *c-fos* levels did not significantly differ across conditions. This could have been potentially caused by low sample size, imaging and/or processing issues. These results support the role of *pth2* as a social density marker, indicating how social cues are encoded in the brain of *Danio rerio*. Overall, the protocol worked as intended however the experiments should be repeated with improvements to reliably assess the impact of social density.

INTRODUCTION

Social animal's brain constantly integrates cues from the environment to regulate interactions with their surroundings and conspecifics. These signals can have different origins and are processed by specialized neural populations that modulate internal states. Neuropeptides, unlike fast-acting neurotransmitters, spread more slowly and broadly to modulate behavioral states over minutes to hours.

In larval zebrafish (*Danio rerio*), the neuropeptide Parathyroid hormone 2 (Pth2) is produced by a small cluster of neurons located in the dorsal thalamus. Its expression is highly sensitive to social context, varying with the presence of conspecifics and mediated by mechanosensory detection of vibrations caused by their swimming.

In addition to *pth2* expression, the activity of *pth2*⁺ neurons may also vary with group size. Immediate early gene *c-fos* is a reliable marker to reveal short-term functional response. Measuring *c-fos* in *pth2*⁺ neurons allows for a direct comparison between the slow transcriptional regulation of neuropeptide expression and the rapid, activity-dependent response of these cells.

In this study, we test two hypotheses: (i) *pth2* expression increases with the number of conspecifics, and (ii) the activation of thalamic *pth2*⁺ neurons, indicated by *c-fos* expression, also

increases with group size. Through expression and cell count analysis, we aim to evaluate whether one or both markers accurately represent social density.

Because *pth2* is a molecular signal that reflects social context in vertebrate, combining its study with *c-fos* offers a way to link long-term transcriptional regulation to short-term neuronal activation. These findings could ultimately clarify how social interactions are translated into molecular signals that regulate neural circuits and behavior.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The zebrafish larvae we used are issued from the breeding of three males and three females. During the first 3 days post-fertilization (dpf), larvae were stored by groups of 50 in six Petri dishes containing a standard E3 medium and maintained at 28°C.

Groups formation for the *pth2* experiment

To facilitate the isolation of the fish and promote a more randomized selection, we anesthetized the fish in ice water. At 5 dpf, we decided to separate the fish into groups of 50, 20, 5, 2 and isolation group.

We created the groups in order from largest to smallest: first the group of 50, then 20, followed by two groups of five, five groups of two, and finally ten isolated fish. We had at least ten fish per group size for our final analysis.

Figure 1| Group formation for the *pth2* experiment. Adult zebrafish (three males and three females) were bred to produce larvae. After 3 days, larvae from six breeding dishes (~ 50 per dish) were redistributed into social groups of 1, 2, 5, 20, or 50 individuals.

The presence or absence of swim bladders, which reflect differences in developmental stage, was taken into consideration.

To randomize the larval selection, each experimenter collected an equal number of larvae for each group size. Between each experimenter, we rotated the breeding dishes to avoid bias related to a specific dish. During selection, we alternated between larvae with and without a swim bladder to balance the developmental stage between the groups.

Samples were incubated at 28°C with a piece of paper between each dish so that the fish from different groups could not see each other.

Groups formation for the *c-fos* experiment

Approximately 100 larvae were first isolated in 48-well plates for two hours so that *c-fos* expression would return to a basal level in the *pth2*⁺ neurons, after the transient activation induced by the presence of other fishes in the breeding dishes. After this period, we randomly selected the fish to create the same groups as for the first experiment, also in decreasing order. Since *c-fos* is a marker of rapid neuronal activity, we left the fish in isolation for 45 minutes in a quiet place, before fixing them.

Figure 2| Group formation for the *c-fos* experiment. Larvae from six dishes (~ 50 per dish) were first isolated individually in 48-well plates for 2 hours to reduce baseline *c-fos* activity. They were then redistributed into social groups of 1, 2, 5, 20, or 50 individuals for the second experiment.

Fixation

From this step, we started the Baier Lab HCR protocol adapted for larvae (annex 1.1 and 2)

First, we fixed the fish from the second experiment by randomly choosing 10 fish from each group. Then, we immersed them in a solution containing 5 mL of 4% paraformaldehyde (PFA). We performed the same procedure on the fish from the first experiment, and we left the fixation act for 24 hours at 4 °C, with gentle shaking.

The *pth2* experiment was performed on the first day since it reflects long-term changes in social context and does not require a precise temporal window. The *c-fos* experiment was carried out the following day, since *c-fos* expression is sensitive to immediate neuronal activation. Performing the *c-fos* experiment separately allowed us to strictly control the timing between isolation, social exposure, and fixation, and to avoid any unintended induction of *c-fos* during the preparation of the *pth2* experiment.

Permeabilization and rehydration of larvae

On the second day, the fixed larvae were washed with DPBST to remove residual paraformaldehyde and stop the fixation process.

The samples were then permeabilized for 10 minutes in 100% methanol (-20°C). This step is important for the subsequent hybridization, as it allows the probes to enter the cells.

After permeabilization, the larvae were gradually rehydrated through a series of 5-minute washes (50%, 25%, 0% methanol). It should be noted that during the washing steps, the used solution was poured into a Falcon tube before disposal, to

ensure that no larvae were accidentally taken up with the pipette.

Hybridization Chain Reaction (Annex 1.1, 2)

HCR (Hybridization Chain Reaction) is an enzyme-free signal amplification method used to detect specific mRNA in cells, like neurons of the larval zebrafish hypothalamus. When the target mRNA is present, the initiator-mRNA complex triggers a chain of hairpin hybridization to build a long fluorescent chain and thereby increase detection signal and resolution for imaging. In these experiments we used probes specific to *pth2* and *cfos* mRNA targets.

Fixed and permeabilized larvae were incubated for 30 minutes in hybridization buffer (37°C, 30 min). After removing the hybridization solution, the larvae were incubated overnight at 37°C in a probe solution, on a gentle rotating shaker, with the tubes placed on their sides for even exposure.

Imaging and fluorescence quantification

For both experiments, larvae were embedded in agarose to maintain a consistent dorsoventral orientation during imaging. Whole-brain Z-stacks were acquired using a two-photon excitation confocal microscope, with a 3 μm spacing between each plane, representing a trade-off between imaging speed and resolution appropriate for the size of the cells. Identical laser and settings were used across all samples. This provided voxel-level fluorescence analysis suitable for quantitative analysis of gene expression.

pth2:

For the *pth2* experiment, preprocessing was performed in Fiji and consisted of a quality check and cropping of the images to restrict the analysis to the thalamus. Quantification was then carried out using custom Python code (Annex 1.5.2) together with the *numpy*, *pandas*, and *tiffle* frameworks, while visualization was performed using *matplotlib* and *seaborn*.

To extract robust intensity-based metrics, we first defined a brain's region of interest and applied a fixed global intensity threshold chosen from intensity histograms for each group size, positioning it just above the background peak to separate noise from the meaningful signal (Annex 1.4). The same value was applied to all stacks. Threshold-based filtering enabled the determination of two metrics: (i) mean

fluorescence intensity (signal strength) and (ii) the total volume of filtered voxels (number of voxels multiplied by physical voxel size, in μm^3), characterizing the spatial extent of the signal. A third metric, manual counting of *pth2*⁺ cells, was performed by three independent blinded observers (Annex 1.5.1), and counts were averaged for each larva. These three metrics effectively complement each other: signal strength, its spatial distribution, and the number of cells expressing the desired marker.

c-fos :

For the *c-fos* experiment, due to a technical issue with the imaging system, DAPI signal for the $n = 20$ and $n = 50$ group samples had to be imaged twice. In contrast to *pth2*, *c-fos* expression was spatially broader and included signal both inside and outside the region of interest identified in the previous experiment. To ensure consistency in quantification across samples, all brains were aligned to a common reference using Advanced Normalization Tools (ANTs) and we checked the alignment manually (Annex 1.3). The reference brain was chosen based on the embedding orientation, symmetry and good intensity contrast. The alignment was performed using the DAPI channel. This allowed fluorescence quantification to be restricted within a single 3D mask corresponding to the average *pth2*⁺ cells location, using *pth2*-stained brains. For each aligned brain, mean fluorescence intensity and total voxel volume above threshold were measured within the masked region, using the same method as in the previous experiment.

Statistical analysis

Statistical analyses were performed in R. For each gene, the different fluorescence parameters were analysed separately (*pth2*: mean intensity, voxel volume and cell count; *c-fos*: mean intensity and voxel volume). For *pth2*, differences among group sizes were assessed by one-way ANOVA followed by TukeyHSD post-hoc test. For *c-fos*, visual inspection and Levene's test indicated strong heteroscedasticity; therefore, Kruskal-Wallis nonparametric tests were applied separately to mean intensity and volume above threshold measures. No post-hoc tests were performed because neither metric was statistically significant. P-values were interpreted relative to an $\alpha = 0.05$ significance threshold.

Because the three fluorescence-based measures were defined a priori and represent

complementary aspects of gene expression rather than exploratory comparisons, no correction for multiple ANOVAs (or Kruskal-Wallis) was applied. The consistency of the results across metrics within each experiment matched the expectation that these measures are indeed related and dependent, supporting the validity of this approach. Within each analysis of *pth2* measures, post-hoc comparisons were adjusted using TukeyHSD function in R, which already controls for multiple pairwise testing.

Experimental design considerations

Due to practical constraints, a fully balanced design (equal number of replicates per group) was not feasible for the largest group sizes. Replication was therefore adjusted to ensure sufficient larvae per condition while maintaining randomization and consistent handling across all groups. This approach allowed reliable comparisons between groups of different sizes while remaining experimentally feasible.

RESULTS

pth2 expression scales with social group size

The representative brain projections allowed for visual qualitative examination and showed that isolated larvae exhibited lower fluorescence signal intensity than those in larger groups (Fig. 3a). Consistent with this observation, manual *pth2*⁺ cell counts revealed that isolated larvae displayed significantly fewer positive neurons compared to those exposed to conspecifics in social groups (Fig. 3b), supporting reduced expression under isolation.

Mean fluorescence intensity also differed significantly across conditions, showing a stepwise increase from smaller to larger groups (Fig. 3c). The strongest signals were observed in the higher-density conditions (20 and 50). The filtered voxel volume followed the same pattern (Fig. 3d), with larger groups exhibiting a broader spatial extent of the *pth2* signal. As a result, intensity, volume, and cell count thoroughly converge to support our first hypothesis: *pth2* expression scales positively with social group size.

Figure 3 | Quantification of *pth2* mRNA fluorescence in the thalamus. **a**, Representative projections of *pth2* fluorescence signal (cyan) for each group size (1, 2, 5, 20, 50 larvae; dorsal view, single coronal plane at the level of the thalamus). Images show the thalamic *pth2*⁺ neuron cluster, with increasing signal observed in larger groups. Scale bar, 100 µm. **b**, Manual cell count of *pth2*⁺ neurons shows a significant increase in the number of expressing cells with group size (ANOVA test: $P = 9,409 \times 10^{-4}$). **c**, Mean fluorescence intensity of *pth2*⁺ neurons also increases with group size (ANOVA test: $P = 7,853 \times 10^{-7}$). **d**, Total voxel volume above threshold reflecting the spatial extent of *pth2* expression shows a similar positive scaling (ANOVA test: $P = 2,114 \times 10^{-6}$). Statistical comparisons were performed using one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey HSD post-hoc tests. Group sizes ranged from $n = 6-7$. Each point represents one larva; boxes indicate the median and interquartile range. Significance is reported as follows: * $P < 0.05$, ** $P < 0.01$ and *** $P < 0.001$.

Figure 4 | Quantification of *c-fos* fluorescence in the thalamic *pth2*⁺ region. **a**, Group-averaged *c-fos* fluorescence signal (magenta) overlaid on the DAPI reference brain (gray) for each group size (1, 2, 5, 20, 50 larvae; dorsal view, single coronal plane at the level of the thalamus). The region of interest corresponds to the average *pth2*⁺ cells location, based on experiment 1. Scale bar, 100 μm . **b**, **c**, Quantification of mean fluorescence intensity (**b**) and total voxel volume above threshold (**c**) of the *c-fos* signal within this region did not reveal significant differences across group sizes (Kruskal-Wallis test: $P > 0.05$). Group sizes ranged from $n = 5$ -8. Each point represents one larva; boxes show the median and interquartile range.

Neuronal activation in *pth2*⁺ neurons does not significantly vary with social group size

Representative mean-brain projections illustrated *c-fos* averaged signal within the brain across group sizes, reflecting its expression (Fig. 4a). Visually, the signal appeared lower in the thalamus of isolated larvae, whereas individuals exposed to conspecifics showed slightly more intense signal. Quantitative analyses of mean fluorescence intensity and signal volume in the region of interest did not reveal difference in *c-fos* expression across group sizes (Fig. 4b, c). Although both measures exhibited a trend toward lower values in isolated larvae, no clear effect of social group size on *pth2*⁺ neurons activation was observed.

DISCUSSION

Our study investigated how the social environment influences *pth2* expression and the activity of *pth2*⁺ neurons in larval zebrafish.

In line with our first hypothesis, we found that *pth2* expression increases with group size and decreases under isolation, supporting the idea

that this neuropeptide serves as a molecular indicator of social context. However, this should be confirmed with experiments including a larger number of individuals. The main limitations of this study were the loss of several samples during manipulation and the exclusion of some images due to missing information, which may have reduced representativeness. The manual cell count performed by multiple observers may also have introduced variability, as overlapping cells made it difficult to determine whether they represented single or multiple cells.

Our second hypothesis regarding *c-fos* activation in *pth2*⁺ neurons according to group size did not reach statistical significance, which may reflect technical limitations. The detection of *c-fos* signal in some images, and the overlap between *c-fos* and *pth2* signals was not exact, as it was based on a mask, which may have caused an under- or overestimation of *pth2*⁺ neuron activation. In addition, the groups of 20 and 50 individuals in the second experiment had to be imaged twice, causing some photobleaching and potentially reducing *c-fos* signal intensity. This may explain the lower values observed in these groups, however, it also leaves open the possibility that

group size may not exert a distinct effect on neural activation.

In future studies, it would be interesting to determine whether there is a limit to group size beyond which *pth2* expression no longer increases, or to investigate how visual stimulation contributes to social coding. Our findings support the conclusions from Anneser et al. (2020) by showing that *pth2* acts as a molecular sensor of social context in zebrafish, with expression increasing in larger groups and decreasing under isolation. Although *c-fos* activation in *pth2*⁺ neurons was not statistically significant, the trend suggests that social experience influences neural activity in this pathway. Together, these results highlight that *pth2* neuropeptide concentration is modulated by the presence or absence of conspecifics, supporting its role as a neuronal marker of the social environment and contributing to our understanding of the neural mechanisms underlying social processing in zebrafish.

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5. BioRender and PowerPoint for illustrations.
6. ChatGPT for Python code generation.
7. AI for syntax and text review of some parts.

ANNEXES

1- METHODS

1.1 - Hybridization Chain Reaction protocol

Objective: visualize mRNA expression thanks to fluorescence in fixed specimens

Principle:

To do this protocol, we need two types of DNA kinetically trapped hairpins (H1 and H2) that can self-assemble if there is an initiator I1.

First, the target mRNA is recognized by the initiator and links to it. The input domain of hairpin 1, which is shown here in orange, binds to the initiator enabling H1 to open and expose his output domain, shown here in red. This new domain is then recognized by Hairpin H2 due to its resemblance to the initiator sequence. H2 hybridizes to H1 and can open and expose its output domain. The process keeps alternating between H1 and H2 until a long chain is formed along the mRNA. Because every hairpin carries a fluorescence tag, this chain produces an amplified signal under the microscope

Figure 5 | Mechanism of the HCR amplification process leading to the fluorescent signal proportional to mRNA quantity. Made with biorender

The full protocol (Annex 2) can be summarized by the steps below

1. Fixation of the specimen with:
 - DPBS, a buffer to keep physiological pH and osmolarity
 - 4% PFA which crosslinks chemically proteins to preserve cellular tissues and locking them into place -> 4%
2. Permeabilization using methanol -20°C
3. Incubation with the pre-hybridization buffer
4. Overnight probe hybridization (adding the
5. initiators)
6. Washes to remove the unbound probes

7. Amplification: addition of H1 and H2 and incubation
8. Washes to clear the excess hairpins

1.2 - Fiji use

We primarily used Fiji to process the imaging results as it allows to do a vast amount of image manipulations. In particular, we used it to:

- Visualize the images and adjust settings to assess quality and brain orientation before proceeding to further analyses.
- Count the *pth2*⁺ cells with the point tool which allowed us to keep track of the already counted cells.
- Crop the images to delimit a perimeter with the fluorescence signal of interest. We targeted the hypothalamus region and used these cropped images in python to quantify fluorescence.
- Verify manually the alignment provided by ANTs algorithm for *c-fos*-stained brains by overlaying the reference and aligned brains, using a different color for each. Ensure that there was no major discrepancy between the brain position.
- Create the mask for *c-fos* fluorescence quantification. We selected a specific zone by drawing a 3D mask around the mean *pth2*⁺ cells location and we interpolated to average these zones. Then we applied the mask to the aligned *c-fos* images for each group to see if *c-fos* is expressed at the same position as *pth2*. Using the same mask for all samples avoids any observer bias.

Figure 6 | Creation and application of the 3D mask for *c-fos* fluorescence quantification. (Top) Average *pth2*⁺ cells location based on three *pth2*-stained brains. (Middle) 3D mask defining the region of interest based on the average *pth2*⁺ cells location. (Bottom) Same region of interest mask applied to *c-fos* images.

1.3 - Alignment algorithm (ANTs)

We used as model the first larva in the group $n = 50$ because it was nicely embedded, with good intensity and symmetry. We then aligned the other images with the algorithm by reshaping the brains to be the most resemblant to the model without changing the intensity values. To do all this process, we used the images with the DAPI channels because there should be less differences between the brains and the fluorescence was more spread out through all the images. Finally, we checked manually with Fiji that all the images were aligned well enough for further analysis, and we took out 3 images that did not work.

Figure 7| Example of brain alignment with ANTs algorithm. A moving brain is registered to the fixed reference brain using the DAPI channel.

1.4 - Voxels and thresholding settings

For both *pth2* and *c-fos* fluorescence quantification, voxel filtering was performed using a single, histogram-based thresholding approach. For each group size, we generated voxel-intensity histograms that consistently displayed two components: a dominant low-intensity peak corresponding to background noise, and a higher-intensity tail representing true fluorescent signal. The threshold was defined at the inflection point between these components, ensuring a conservative but robust separation of noise from biologically meaningful fluorescence. The same threshold value was then applied uniformly across samples within each experiment to compute suprathreshold voxel volume and mean intensity.

Figure 8| Example of voxel extraction. Raw fluorescence image (left) and threshold-filtered voxels used for quantification (right).

Figure 9| Voxel intensity histograms for *pth2* (left) and *c-fos* (right), showing separation between background noise (left peak) and true fluorescent signal (right tail). The chosen threshold (red vertical line) corresponds to the inflection point between these components.

1.5 - Python codes

We used ChatGPT to help generate the following Python codes and we carefully checked, adjusted, and validated the final versions below.

1.5.1 - Anonymization and blinding

To facilitate blinded manual cell count, we used the following code to anonymize the files.

```
source_folder =
"/Users/.../original_files"

output_folder =
"/Users/.../ anonymous_files"

repartition_file =
"/Users/.../repartition.csv"
# Creating the output folder
```

```

os.makedirs(output_folder,
exist_ok=True)

# List of original files
files = os.listdir(source_folder)
files.sort()

# Initialising the dictionary to store
links between original and new names
mapping = {}

# Copy and rename each file anonymously
for f in files :
    ext = os.path.splitext(f)[1]
    new_name =
f"{uuid.uuid4().hex}{ext}"

shutil.copy2(os.path.join(source_folder,
f), os.path.join(output_folder,
new_name))
    mapping[new_name] = f

# Save correspondence in a CSV file
with open(repartition_file, "w",
newline='', encoding="utf-8") as
csvfile:
    writer = csv.writer(csvfile)

writer.writerow(["anonymous_file",
"original_file"])
    for anonymous, original in
mapping.items():
        writer.writerow([anonymous,
original])

```

1.5.2 - Fluorescence quantification

```

# Path to the imaging files
FOLDER =
Path('/Users/.../imaging_files')

# Set to True if c-fos data, False if
pth2 data
CFOS_DATA = True

# For output files
OUTPUT = FOLDER / 'results2'

OUTPUT.mkdir(exist_ok=True)

# For c-fos fluorescence quantification
MASK_PATH =
Path('/Users/.../3D_mask.tif')

# Mask preparation
mask = tiff.imread(MASK_PATH)
mask = mask.astype(bool)
mask = np.moveaxis(mask, 0, 2)

# Voxel parameters

```

```

width = 1.1861
height = 1.1861
depth = 3.000

voxel_volume = width * height * depth

```

HELPER FUNCTIONS

```

def parse_group_size(filename: str):
    """Group size extraction from
filename"""
    match = re.search(r'n(\d+)',
filename)
    if match:
        return int(match.group(1))

def read_lsm(path: Path):
    """Image reading from path"""
    arr = tiff.imread(path)
    return arr

def prepare_image(img : np.ndarray):
    """Prepare image for 2D
visualization"""
    if img.ndim > 3:
        return img[:, 0, :, :]
    return img

```

MAIN LOOP

```

threshold = 8 # Our threshold value: 12
for pth2, 8 for c-fos

results = []
files = []
files.extend(sorted(FOLDER.glob("*.nii")
))
files.extend(sorted(FOLDER.glob("*.tif")
))
files.extend(sorted(FOLDER.glob("*.lsm")
))

for file in files: # Replace to
.lsm/.tif if needed (.nii -> only for c-
fos data)

    # Image reading and preparation
    group_size =
parse_group_size(file.name)

    if CFOS_DATA:
        data =
np.array(nib.load(file).get_fdata())
        rot = np.rot90(data, k=3,
axes=(0, 1))
        prepared_image = rot * mask
    else:
        data = read_lsm(file)
        prepared_image =
prepare_image(data)
    # Thresholding

```

```

    filter_mask = prepared_image >
threshold

    if CFOS_DATA:
        data_thresholded =
prepared_image[filter_mask]
        image_thresholded =
prepared_image * (prepared_image >
threshold)
    else:
        data_thresholded =
prepared_image[filter_mask]
        image_thresholded =
prepared_image * filter_mask

    # Statistics for intensity and
voxels
    mean_intensity =
np.mean(data_thresholded)
    voxels_above_threshold =
np.sum(filter_mask)
    volume_above_threshold =
voxels_above_threshold * voxel_volume

    results.append({
        "file": file.name,
        "group_size": group_size,
        "mean_intensity":
mean_intensity,
        "volume_above_threshold":
volume_above_threshold,
    })
results_df = pd.DataFrame(results)

```

2 - HCR PROTOCOL (Baier Lab for larvae)

Molecular instruments HCR protocol can be downloaded from here. We have modified the protocol to enable registration of the results to the MapZeBrain atlas with multiple rounds of hybridization (similar to Lovett Barron et al. 2020).

Storage conditions

Store HCR probe sets, HCR amplifiers, HCR probe hybridization buffer, and HCR probe wash buffer at -20°C. Store HCR amplification buffer at 4°C. On the bench top, keep stock solutions on ice. Make sure all solutions are well mixed before use.

Buffers :

10× DPBS (Dulbecco's PBS – PBS without MgCl and without CaCl)

This modified PBS is recommended by Molecular instruments, as it reduces the autofluorescence. We buy the ×10 DPBS (to be diluted with ddw).

1× DPBST (for 500 mL) protect from light

- 50 mL of 10×DBPS
- 5 mL of 10% Tween20
- 445 mL of ddw

4% PFA in DPBS

- 10 mL of 16% PFA
- 30 mL of 1×DPBS

5×SSCT (for 40 mL) protect from light

- 10 mL of 20×SSC 400 μL 10% Tween20
- 30 mL of ddw

10% Tween20 (for 50 mL), protect from light.

- 5 mL Tween20
- 45 mL ddw

Fixation and permeabilization of whole-mount larvae

For optimal alignment reference we use HuC:H2b-GCaMP6s larvae. The larvae should be fixed at 6dpf and processed immediately to the HCR protocol. Long term storage in MeOH is possible but results in tissue deformation that prevents alignment to the atlas (this will not affect the HCR efficiency). Keep the larvae protected from light throughout the entire procedure to prevent loss of the GCaMP fluorescent signal.

Day 1

1. Fix 6dpf HuC:H2b-GCaMP6s larvae in 1 mL of fresh 4% paraformaldehyde (PFA) in DPBS for 24h at 4°C (1-10 larvae per 1ml) with gentle shaking. Make sure to fix for 20-25 hours. Shorter fixation results in loss of the GCaMP signal during the HCR protocol and tissue deformation.

Day2

2. Wash larvae 3 × 5 min with 1 mL of DPBST to stop the fixation.

3. Permeabilize for 10min with cold 100% methanol in -20°C. The methanol should be cooled to -20°C before use.

4. Wash for 5min in 50% methanol/50% DPBST (prepare fresh).

5. Wash for 5min in 25% methanol/75% DPBST (prepare fresh).

6. Wash for 5 × 5min DPBST. Prob Hybridization

7. Pre-hybridize with 500 μL (we used 1,5ml) of probe hybridization buffer for 30 min at 37°C. Pre-heat the hybridization buffer to 37 °C before use. CAUTION : probe hybridization buffer contains formamide, a hazardous material.

8. Prepare probe solution by adding 2 pmol of each probe set (e.g. 2 μL of 1 μM stock) to 500 μL of probe hybridization buffer at the 37 °C room with tubes lying on their side on the shaker.

9. Remove the pre-hybridization solution and add the probe solution.

10. Incubate the larvae overnight (12–16 h) at the 37 °C room with tubes lying on their side on the shaker (gentle shaking).

Day 3

11. Remove excess probes by washing embryos/larvae 4 × 15 min with 500 μL (we used 1ml) of probe wash buffer at the 37 °C room with tubes lying on their side on the shaker (gentle shaking). Pre-heat probe wash buffer to 37 °C before use CAUTION : probe wash buffer contains formamide, a hazardous material 1/5.

12. Wash larvae 2 × 5 min with 5× SSCT at room temperature. It is possible to wait a few hours before continuing to the amplification stage.

Amplification

13. Pre-amplify larvae with 500 μL of amplification buffer for 30 min at room temperature. Equilibrate amplification buffer to room temperature before use.

14. Separately prepare 30 pmol of hairpin h1 and 30 pmol of hairpin h2 by snap cooling 10 μL of 3 μM stock (heat at 95 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 90 seconds and cool to room temperature in a dark drawer for 30 min). HCR hairpins h1 and h2 are provided in hairpin storage buffer ready for snap cooling. h1 and h2 should be snap cooled in separate tubes. If only staining one larva, the volumes can be reduced to a quarter. Prepare hairpin solution by adding snap-cooled h1 hairpins and snap-cooled h2 hairpins to 500 μL of amplification buffer at room temperature. When staining only one larva, the volumes can be reduced to a quarter.

15. Remove the pre-amplification solution and add the hairpin solution.

16. Incubate the embryos/larvae overnight (12–16 h) in the dark at room temperature.

Day 4

17. Remove excess hairpins by washing with for 3 \times 20min with 500 μL of 5 \times SSCT at room temperature.

18. Mount the larvae in agarose for imaging.

Additional procedures for stripping and re-staining the same larvae with new HCR probes - [> not used here.](#)

References listed in the Baier Lab (larvae) HCR protocol

- Dirks, Robert M., and Niles A. Pierce. "Triggered amplification by hybridization chain reaction." *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 101.43 (2004): 15275-15278.
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- Trivedi, Vikas, et al. "Multidimensional quantitative analysis of mRNA expression within intact vertebrate embryos." *Development* 145.1 (2018).
- Choi, Harry MT, Maayan Schwarzkopf, and Niles A. Pierce. "Multiplexed Quantitative In Situ Hybridization with Subcellular or Single-Molecule Resolution Within Whole-Mount Vertebrate Embryos: qHCR and dHCR Imaging (v3. 0)." *In Situ Hybridization Protocols*. Humana, New York, NY, 2020. 159-178.